

Esterification of phthalic anhydride with *n*-butanol using homogeneous catalysts

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Abstract : The kinetics of esterification of phthalic anhydride (PAN) with *n*-butanol (BuOH) has been investigated using *para*-toluene sulphonic acid (*p*-TSA) and methane sulphonic acid (MSA) as the catalysts. The effect of various parameters such as temperature, catalyst concentration and mole ratio of reactants has been systematically investigated. The kinetic parameters (rate constant, activation energy and frequency factor) have been determined.

Keywords : Esterification kinetics, phthalic anhydride, *para*-toluene sulphonic acid, methane sulphonic acid.

Introduction

Di-*n*-butyl phthalate (DBP), synthesized by esterification of PAN with BuOH, is widely used plasticizer after di-octyl phthalate (DOP). Synthesis of DBP involves two steps : (a) formation of mono-*n*-butyl phthalate (MBP) and (b) formation of DBP. The overall reaction is an equilibrium reaction wherein water gets formed as one of the reaction products. The first step is spontaneous and does not require catalyst. However, second step needs catalyst to accelerate the rate of reaction. Therefore, it is essential to select a proper catalyst and to remove water continuously for greater ester yields. An information on synthesis of DBP is scarce unlike to DOP. Voluminous reports are available in literature pertaining to synthesis of DOP using various homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts such as sulphuric acid¹, *p*-TSA², titanates and zirconates^{3,4}, heteropoly acid⁵, ionic liquids⁶ and solid superacidic catalyst⁷. Very few reports are available in literature wherein DBP has been synthesized using red algae-bangia atropurpurea⁸, acid functionalized ionic liquid⁶, heteropoly acids⁵.

Therefore, in the present work, a systematic investigation of esterification of PAN with BuOH has been undertaken using *p*-TSA and MSA as the catalysts. The objectives of the present study are : (i) to study kinetics of esterification reaction using *p*-TSA and MSA and (ii) to compare the performance of *p*-TSA and MSA with respect to rate of reaction, amount of catalyst required and color of the reaction product.

Experimental

Chemicals :

PAN and BuOH were obtained from I.G. Petrochemical Ltd., India and Andhra Petrochemical Ltd., India, as the gift samples, respectively. *p*-TSA and MSA were obtained from S. D. Finechem Ltd., Mumbai. All the chemicals were used as obtained from suppliers.

Experimental set up :

Experiments were carried out in a glass reactor of 250 ml capacity, equipped with glass stirrer and a thermometer pocket. Dean and Stark apparatus with a condenser was connected to the reactor to remove the water formed during the reaction, and to drive the reaction towards product side. The temperature of the system was maintained constant (± 1 °C) by means of a relay heating circuit in an oil bath.

Procedure :

In a typical run, the MBP was prepared by reacting equimolar quantities of PAN and BuOH at 120 °C. The second mole of alcohol (BuOH) was then added to the reactor together with a catalyst when predetermined temperature was reached. The samples of 2 ml were withdrawn, ice cooled and titrated against alcoholic KOH with phenolphthalein as indicator to analyze the reaction progress.

Analysis :

The reaction was monitored by chemical as well as

instrumental analysis. In chemical analysis the reaction samples were titrated against alcoholic KOH solution, i.e. the number of acid groups titrated against a base, which is a simple acid-base titration, whereas for gas chromatography (GC) analysis the samples were diluted and neutralised by an alkali solution and then injected into a gas chromatograph (model Chemito), using a flame ionization detector and an Oracle integrator, with a S.S. column packed with 5% OV-17 on Chromosorb WHP (length 2 m, I.D. 1/8 inches). Chemical analysis was used to get information on the reacted acid groups and GC on the unreacted alcohol remaining in the reaction mixture.

Results and discussion

Reaction pathway :

The esterification of PAN with BuOH involves two steps as shown in following chemical reactions :

First step :

Second step :

Overall reaction :

The first reaction is instantaneous which gets completed within 15 min in the absence of catalyst while second reaction is catalytic wherein water gets formed as one of the reaction products.

Effect of agitation :

The effect of speed of agitation on conversion of MBP was studied at the temperature of 140 °C and a catalyst loading of 1% (w/w) for MSA. It has been seen that the speed of agitation has no appreciable effect on the conversion of MBP over a range of 800–1200 rpm. Therefore, all the experiments were carried out at a constant speed of agitation of 1000 rpm.

Kinetic studies :

Reaction model :

The following reaction can be written :

where A, B, C and D stand for MBP, BuOH, DBP and water, respectively.

Since during the course of reaction, water formed is continuously removed, the reversible reaction becomes irrelevant. Therefore, the rate expression can be written as follows :

$$-\frac{dC_A}{dt} = k C_A^x C_B^y \quad (2)$$

where, x is an order in the MBP, y is an order in BuOH. The specific rate constant k could be considered as a function of the catalyst concentration as $k = k \times [\text{catalyst}]^z$, z being an order in the catalyst. An integral method of analysis could be used for estimating rate constant and order of the reaction wherein we guess order with respect to each reactant is one. Thus integrating eq. (2) between the limits C_{A0} to C_A from time 0 to t , we get following rate expression :

$$\ln \frac{C_B}{C_A} = k(C_{B0} - C_{A0})t + \ln \frac{C_{A0}}{C_{B0}} \quad (3)$$

where C_{A0} and C_{B0} are initial concentrations of MBP and BuOH, respectively. A plot of $\ln \frac{C_B}{C_A}$ vs time, therefore should give a straight line showing first order dependence on the concentration of both reactants with a slope as $k(C_{B0} - C_{A0})$.

Effect of temperature :

Experiments were carried out using *p*-TSA and MSA as a catalyst at three different temperatures (120, 130 and 140 °C). The molar ratio of reactants was kept constant at 1 : 1.15 while MSA and *p*-TSA concentration were maintained at 1% (w/w) and 1.2% (w/w), respectively. Fig. 1A and 1B show the second order kinetic plots for MSA and *p*-TSA, respectively. The specific value of k (rate constant) was determined by the slope of the lines at different temperatures. The straight line obtained in each case indicates the reaction to be of first order with respect to both, MBP and BuOH. Fig. 2 shows the Arrhenius plot for both, MSA and *p*-TSA. The Arrhenius equation parameters, E (activation energy, kcal mol⁻¹) and A (frequency factor, L mol⁻¹ min⁻¹) were determined (Table 1) and following rate expression have been obtained for MSA and *p*-TSA.

Fig.1. Second order kinetic plot.

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plot.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters

Catalyst	Temp. (°C)	E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	A (L mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
MSA	120, 130, 140	20.77	1.75×10^9
<i>p</i> -TSA	120, 130, 140	17.75	2.42×10^7

Effect of catalyst loading :

Fig. 3A and 3B show the effect of catalyst loading on

Fig. 3. Effect of catalyst loading.

Fig. 4. Effect of mole ratio of reactants.

the conversion of MBP at 140 °C and 1 : 1.15 molar ratio of the reactants for MSA and *p*-TSA, respectively. It has been seen that an increase in catalyst concentration increases the rate of reaction for early stage of the reaction. However, the data points merge together as reaction tends to equilibrium. It has also been observed that the color of the end product increases with an increase in catalyst concentration. Therefore, it is necessary to select suitable concentration of catalyst for synthesis of DBP. In the present work, optimum concentrations of MSA and *p*-TSA were found to be 0.75% (w/w) and 1% (w/w), respectively.

Effect of mole ratio of reactants :

Experiments were conducted at three different molar ratios of MBP and BuOH (1 : 1.12, 1 : 1.15 and 1 : 1.3) at 140 °C using MSA and *p*-TSA. The MSA and *p*-TSA concentrations were kept constant at 0.75% (w/w) and 1% (w/w), respectively. Fig. 4A and 4B show effect of variation of molar ratio of MBP to BuOH on the conversion of MBP for MSA and *p*-TSA, respectively. It has

been seen that the conversion of MBP increase with an increase in the molar ratio.

Conclusions

The conclusions of the present work are as follows :

(i) The esterification of reaction of PAN with BuOH essentially follows overall second order kinetics, first order with respect to each reactant using MSA and *p*-TSA as a catalyst. The corresponding rate expressions obtained are as follows :

$$-r_A = 1.75 \times 10^9 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{10452}{T}\right)} C_A C_B$$

$$-r_A = 2.42 \times 10^7 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{8933}{T}\right)} C_A C_B$$

(ii) Under optimized condition, the rate of reaction using MSA has been found higher (~1.3 times) as compared to *p*-TSA. However, interestingly, the color indexes for both the catalysts for final reaction mixture on the Gardener scale were found to be 4.

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